

(10 g) was heated on a water bath for 2 h. Acrylic acid(3e, f) (1 g) was added to the above clear solution and stirred at room temperature for 36 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into water (50 ml) and the solution was neutralised with sodium bicarbonate, when pyranoquinolin-2-one was separated as pale yellow solid. It was filtered, dried and sublimed at 280° under reduced pressure. M.p., yield, ir and analytical data of 4a-f are given in Table 1. Mass spectral data are given in Table 2.

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Synthesis of Some 3-Arylazo-1-aza-2-phenylpyrrocoline Derivatives

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1-Aza-2-phenylpyrrocolinium bromide (1) has been synthesised¹ and the greater electrophilicity of position 3 over position 1 in the azapyrrocoline nucleus has been established by nitration² and ethoxy methylation reactions³. A calculation based on the FEMO theory has also reached the same conclusion⁴. We report here the synthesis of some 3-arylazo-1-aza-2-phenylpyrrocolines (2) to adduce further support on greater electrophilicity of position 3.

All the compounds were synthesised in excellent yield by the reaction of different aryldiazonium chlorides with 1-aza-2-phenylpyrrocoline. The structures of the compounds were confirmed by their elemental and spectral analysis. The infrared spectra of the compounds exhibit bands in the region 1630-1590 cm⁻¹ due to N=N stretching. The diazo compounds absorb light in the range, 366-395 nm due to n-π* transition⁵. Both the values of

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF AZO COMPOUNDS (2)

X	M.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	λ _{max} nm	ε _{max} × 10 ⁻⁴	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
H	125	70	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₄	380	0.694	75.98 (76.51)	4.50 (4.69)	18.50 (18.79)
p-CH ₃	90	75	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₄	395	1.058	76.28 (76.92)	4.98 (5.12)	17.64 (17.94)
o-Cl	135	80	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₄ Cl	387	0.591	68.12 (68.57)	3.92 (3.90)	16.68 (16.84)
p-Cl	155	80	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₄ Cl	389	0.993	67.98 (68.57)	3.79 (3.90)	16.50 (16.84)
o-OMe	98	90	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	397	0.912	72.82 (73.17)	4.71 (4.87)	16.85 (17.07)
p-OMe	120	70	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	366	0.912	72.95 (73.17)	4.55 (4.87)	16.75 (17.07)
m-NO ₂	115	85	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂	370	0.898	65.97 (66.47)	3.61 (3.79)	19.91 (20.40)
p-NO ₂	127	65	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂	370	0.885	65.87 (66.47)	3.59 (3.79)	19.86 (20.40)
p-SO ₃ H	142	75	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ SO ₃	377	0.586	59.90 (60.31)	3.61 (3.70)	14.80 (14.81)
o-COOH	160	80	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂	372	0.901	69.81 (70.17)	3.98 (4.09)	16.12 (16.97)
p-NH ₂	132	65	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ N ₄	371	0.679	78.85 (74.18)	4.12 (4.22)	21.92 (21.62)

absorption maximum and extinction coefficient are found to be substituent dependent. The values of extinction coefficient are found to change in the order *p*-methyl > *o*-methoxy > *p*-methoxy > *o*-carboxy > *m*-nitro > *p*-nitro > *o*-chloro > *p*-sulphonic acid > *p*-chloro. It is found that these values do not change in a regular order and therefore could not be correlated with Hammett's sigma values. The values of absorption maxima of 3-arylidene derivatives of 2-phenylpyrrocoline show similar type of behaviour⁶.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in an open capillary in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 389 spectrophotometer. Uv spectra (ethanol) were taken on a Toshniwal RL 02 spectrophotometer.

1-Aza-2-phenyl-3-arylazopyrrocoline (2) : 1-Aza-2-phenylpyrrocolinium bromide (1.08 g) was dissolved in water and cooled in ice bath. A mixture of concentrated HCl and aniline (1 : 1) was prepared and the resulting hydrochloride was dissolved in water. An aqueous solution of calculated amount of sodium nitrite was added to the hydrochloride solution in an ice bath. The whole mixture was then added to the solution of azopyrrocolinium bromide in an ice bath and magnetically stirred for 0.5 h. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol-water mixture (70%), m.p. 125° (Found : C, 75.98 ; H, 4.5 ; N, 18.52. C₁₈H₈N₄ requires C, 76.51 ; H, 4.69 ; N, 18.79%) ; λ_{max} (EtOH) 380 nm (ε_{max} = 0.699 × 10⁴). Other azo compounds were prepared by the same method taking different substituted anilines. The analytical data are given in Table 1.

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Studies on Antitubercular Agents. Preparation of 1-(4-Methoxybenzoyl)-2-benzalhydrazine and 2-Aryl-3-(4-methoxybenzamido)-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone

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SEVERAL methods for the synthesis of 4-thiazolidinones have been reported¹⁻⁴. The hydrazones of aromatic or heterocyclic aldehyde/ketone react with α-mercapto acids in benzene to give a variety of substituted-4-thiazolidinone. The present communication is intended to report the reaction of thiomalic acid with hydrazones (1) of 4-methoxybenzhydrazide, and *in vitro* tuberculostatic activity of the resulting 5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones (2). The structure of the title compounds (1 and 2) were confirmed by elemental analysis and ir spectra.

Experimental

1-(4-Methoxybenzoyl)-2-benzal hydrazine (1) : The solution of 4-methoxybenzhydrazide⁵ (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%, 25 ml) was added to benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) in ethanol (95%, 15 ml). Contents were refluxed for 3 h, cooled, filtered, dried and crystallised from 95% ethanol (84%), m.p. 210° (Found : N, 10.90. C₁₅H₁₄N₂O₂ requires N, 11.02%).